

Ancient state of Urartu

also known as “Biainili”

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Entry tags: Hurrian Religions, Urartian Religions, Assyrian Religions, Anatolian Religions, Religious Group, Mesopotamian Religions

Urartu developed from a series of small chiefdoms spread out on the Armenian Plateau, and had its capital established by Sarduri I on the Eastern shores of Lake Van during the mid 9th century BCE. From what today is the modern city of Van, the royal dynasty created by Sarduri ruled until the first half of the 6th century BCE. At one point the main antagonist of the Neo-Assyrian Empire, Urartian territories stretched from Lake Sevan to the southern shore of Lake Urmia, and as far West as the sources of the Euphrates. Urartu's core topography sets it apart from most states of the ancient Near East. Lake Van lies 1,680 m above sea level, and the mountains rise abruptly from the southern and western sides of the lake. This particular part of the Armenian Plateau is an area of intersecting mountain chains, characterised by the presence of depressions separated by highland areas. The result of this particular topography is a series of irregular pockets of land. The expansion of the Urartian state is characterised by the need to secure arable land and resources. Mostly known for their metalwork and their fortifications, Urartians had a well established religion with Haldi at the head of the pantheon. Although most Urartian temples and inscriptions are dedicated to him, there are dozens of other gods mentioned in the texts. Teisheba and Siuini, both wider spread in the Ancient Near East, are the most important deities after Haldi. Unfortunately, as with most archaeological datasets, our understanding of Urartu is limited. The belief system centred on Haldi is closely connected to the royal family and the elite, and we do not know to what degree it permeated the rest of the society.

Date Range: 850 BCE - 580 BCE

Region: Urartu

Region tags: Caucasus, Iran, Transnational, Armenia, Turkey, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, Anatolia

The ancient Urartian state and the modern regions.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Salvini, M. 1995. *Geschichte und Kultur der Urartäer*, Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft.
- Source 2: Kroll, S., Gruber, C., Hellwag, U., Roaf, M., Zimansky, P. 2012. *Biainili-Urartu: the proceedings of the symposium held in Munich 12-14 October 2007 / Tagungsbericht des Münchner Symposiums 12.-14. Oktober 2007*, *Acta Iranica* 51, Leuven: Peeters.
- Source 3: Çifçi, A. 2018. Religion and Kingship Ideology: God Haldi and Urartian Monarch, *Ancient West & East* 17, 119-141.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/ecut/index.html>

– Source 1 Description: The open-access electronic Corpus of Urartian Texts (eCUT), a sub-project of the Munich Open-access Cuneiform Corpus Initiative (MOCCI), is based on Mirjo Salvini's 'Corpus dei testi urartei' (2008-2018). The texts are adapted, revised, lemmatized, and translated into English by Birgit Christiansen.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Assyrian empire; Neo-Hittite states; political entities across the Armenian plateau, including tribal communities

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: We know the names of dozens of gods worshiped in the Urartian territories, at least some of them are probably the local deities of the territories conquered by Urartu. There are also a few temples dedicated to other gods apart from Haldi. Wider cultural contacts and traditions are represented by the worship of Teisheba and Siuini, the storm god and the sun god, respectively, of the Hurrian pantheon.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: An example of this are the alliances with some of the Neo-Hittite states. Urartu also relied on trade to supply some raw materials, so we can safely assume neutral contact driven by economic factors.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Assyrian sources mention internal uprisings within the Urartian state, which could have easily translated into violence.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Urartu was the main antagonist of the Neo-Assyrian empire for the second half of the 9th century BCE and most of the 8th century. Although often this translated into a proxy war, we have numerous accounts of violent clashes between the two states. Urartu also aggressively expanded its territory through military campaigns, conquering smaller political entities spread across the Armenian Plateau.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Safe to assume that an individual being born into a family worshipping Haldi will be automatically part of that religious group.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Conquest - the cult of Haldi is introduced into new regions through military conquest. Although we do not know exactly who would be required to adhere to the new god, and through which mechanisms, it would be necessary for certain parts of the local society in dealing with the new rulers.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Every action of the Urartian kings is made for Haldi, and through the grace of Haldi at the same time. We have numerous temples, gates and stelae dedicated to Haldi by the rulers.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
– Yes

Notes: The king has the power to dictate new ritual practices and set up punishments in the form of curses. This are typically prerogatives of the head clergy. We have no information on religious specialists in Urartu, although it is safe to assume they existed and carried out most of the ritual practices, which usually take the form of animal sacrifices.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
– Yes

Notes: We have little information on this, although we know the king nominates governors through official actions which are always done for Haldi and through the grace of Haldi. Safe to assume that those governors have to adhere to the same belief system.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population,

numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have sufficient data from enough Urartian sites to draw general conclusions, however, we can calculate this for Ayanis, where the temple complex represents 1.5% percent of the fortified site, and the temple itself makes up for 0.28%.

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 190.44

Notes: The largest Urartian temples measure 13.8 x 13.8 metres.

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Highest preserved wall measures five metres, in Ayanis. The original height is estimated to be have been ca. 15 metres. See Altan Çilingiroğlu's "Urartian Temples", in Biainili-Urartu The Proceedings of the Symposium held in Munich 12-14 October 2007, edited by Kroll, S. et all, 2012, Leuven, Peeters Publishers, 295-307.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 164.6

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: Iconography is mostly known from the bronze items found in temples.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: There are pilgrimages undertaken by the king and the crown prince to the main temple of Haldi, in Muşasir, located outside Urartian territory.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There potentially are secondary burials, although we have insufficient data to recognise them as such. For example, the rock carved royal tombs contain multiple rooms, with niches on the walls for funerary urns, and sarcophagus bases on the floor. These tombs were designed for a multiple individuals, however we cannot know if secondary burials were later added.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:
– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:
– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:
– Yes

↳ Valuable items:
– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):
– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):
– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
– No

↳ Other grave goods:
– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: On some inscriptions there are curse formulas, which describe divine punishments.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Uratian kings often follow Haldi in battle, it is the god who sets out with his spear and the army follows.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are geographical features, mountains for example, which have god like status.
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Sacrifices are described for these beings, suggesting they have the power to influence the world, although we do not know in which way.

- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Geographical

Notes: Some deities are likely worshiped only in small geographical areas (certain valleys for example), with overlapping regional and transregional gods.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The curses affect those who damage the inscriptions or alter them in any way, or those who claim they commissioned them or the actions celebrated on the inscriptions.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The most common term used to describe the punishment is "annihilation", which sometimes includes the offspring.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unlikely; in the inscriptions there are instances where castration is performed as punishment for enemies.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unlikely; there are no notable absences in the archaeozoological or archaeobotanical records.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:
– Field doesn't know

↳ To out-groups:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Destroyed:
– Yes

Notes: Animal sacrifices are a predominant feature of the Urartian ritual practice.

↳ Other:
– Yes [specify]: Valuable bronze objects are dedicated to Haldi in the temples, often highly decorated.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Urartian temples are often surrounded by a courtyard dedicated to ritual practises, and we have examples of open air sanctuaries with space for gatherings. Large scale rituals took part in those locations, however, it is unclear how often they took place and who were the participants.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– I don't know

Notes: Further analysis of burned residues from the temple complexes are needed.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: There is no consensus on how to best describe Urartu, as it has been defined an empire by some scholars. To stick to the definitions used here, it being an empire would require that the regions brought under Urartian control would have contained polities which could be defined as states. This would be difficult to prove with the information currently at our disposal.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some of the Urartian centres contain large storage rooms for grains and other produce, however, we cannot say how they would be used in case of a famine.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: To certain elements of the society. For example, the presence of inscriptions implies the existence of an educated scribal class, which would require training.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: We have a few clay tablets and bullae from the reign of Rusa son of Argišti (first half of the 7th century BCE) which highlight the existence of a formal bureaucratic apparatus. That was a moment of reorganisation of the Urartian state, and we have no similar evidence from earlier centuries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 680 BCE - 580 BCE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Very likely that both Urartian state officials and private citizens had dealings with the Neo-Assyrian bureaucratic system.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Notes: The existence of barracks and garrisons suggest the continuous presence of soldiers.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: The Urartian language is related to only one other known language, Hurrian, which is attested in northern Mesopotamia in the second millennium BCE

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Assyrian language; there are several bilingual inscriptions, in Urartian and Assyrian, and interactions between both ruling elites and private citizens of the two ancient states are assumed.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know